

Training and Fostering Civil Servants in Hoa Binh Province

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Abstract: Training and fostering civil servants is one of the activities aimed at improving the quality of the contingent of civil servants and public employees. This activity has always been focused by localities, especially in recent years. Hoa Binh is one of the localities, implementing the Party and State's policies in training and fostering. The article focuses on clarifying the situation of training and fostering civil servants in Hoa Binh province. On that basis, the author proposes a number of solutions to further accelerate this activity.

Keywords: Hoa Binh, fostering, civil servants, training

I. INTRODUCTION

Training and fostering civil servants is one of the important stages in our Party civil servants work. This is a very difficult and complex work, requiring science and art. From the very first days of the establishment of the Soviet Government, VI Lenin had attached great importance to the training and fostering civil servants and thought that this work was decisive for success or failure in the implementation of policies and guidelines of one party and one state. VI Lenin once wrote in the article "The urgent tasks of our movement" (1900): "In history, no class has ever gained dominance, if it could not produce, among their ranks the political leaders, the vanguards who were capable of organizing and leading the movement" [1]. During his life, President Ho Chi Minh always attaches great importance to training and fostering civil servants. Resolution No. 26-NQ / TW, dated May 19, 2018, of the Seventh Conference of the XII Central Executive Committee on "Focusing on building a contingent of civil servants at all levels, especially strategic level, enough qualified, capacity and prestige, on par with the task" also affirmed that the civil servants' opinion was the decisive factor in the success or failure of the revolution; civil servants work is the "key" stage of the work of building the Party and the political system. Therefore, training and fostering civil servants is the most important task of our Party at present. It should be conducted regularly, carefully, scientifically and effectively.

II. THE CONTENT

2.1. The situation of training and fostering civil servants in Hoa Binh province

Hoa Binh is a mountainous province with an important strategic position in the gateway area of the capital and the northwest mountainous provinces. Implementing Central Resolution 5 (Session IX) "On renewing and improving the quality of the grassroots political system in communes, wards and towns", Hoa Binh Provincial Party Committee has issued plans and directing documents to Party committees at all levels actively build and consolidate the political system at the grassroots level, attaching importance to building and improving the quality of grassroots civil servants. Applying creatively and developing the views of Marxism-Leninism on civil servants work in general, the training and fostering civil servants in particular to Vietnam's conditions, President Ho Chi Minh Minh always thinks: "Civil servants is the root of all jobs" [2]; "Every job that succeeds or fails, is due to good or poor civil servants. That is a certain truth" [3]; At the same time, he also attaches great importance to the role of civil servants: "Civil servants are the ones who bring the policies of the Party and the Government to the people to understand and implement. At the same time, bring the situation of the people to the Party and the Government to understand, to set the right policy. Therefore, the civil servants is the root of all jobs. Therefore, training civil servants is the Party's original job" [4].

From 2015, Hoa Binh Provincial Party Committee set a target of striving until 2020: 100% civil servants at commune level have high school education, trained and fostered in political theory, knowledge of state management and professional expertise, of which 90% have an intermediate degree in political theory or higher and 70% have an intermediate professional or higher degree. Thanks to that, the contingent of civil servants at communes, wards and townships (referred to as grassroots cadres) of Hoa Binh has been constantly strengthened and gradually improved their quality, operational efficiency, basically satisfying required the task. The number of young cadres with university and

college degrees has increased, while retired cadres holding leadership and managerial positions has decreased. Currently, the total number of full-time officials and civil servants of the whole province is 4,001. In which, female cadres are 653 (16.3%), ethnic minorities 3,408 (85.2%). University and college degrees 550 (13.8%); intermediate level 1,923 (48.1%); primary level 242 (6.1%); Untrained 1,286 (32.1%). Political theory level: advanced 12 (3%); intermediate level 2,032 (50.8%); primary 765 (19.1%); Untrained 1,192 (29.8%). The number of grassroots members for the 2010-2015 term is 2,796 comrades, of which 498 are female (17.8%). Deputies of the People's Council at grassroots level are 5,207, of which 1,147 females (22%) [5].

Not only increasing the number, the grassroots cadres of Hoa Binh have matured in all aspects. Officers working directly with the people understand the customs, customs and psychology of the people; know to preserve and promote good points, national identity and overcome backward and negative practices; mobilize the masses to well perform the local political tasks, develop socio-economic, ensure national defense and security, and build a new countryside. The face of rural Hoa Binh is renewed, people's lives have been improved. The political system at the grassroots level has been consolidated and increasingly consolidated. The activities of the grassroots government were put in order, more effective and effective, overcoming the overlap in functions and tasks. Supervisory activities of the People's Council, Fatherland Front and political-social organizations have been gradually promoted. Democracy at the grassroots is increasingly focused, ensuring the promotion of the people's ownership.

Hoa Binh Party Committee and government always attach great importance to the work of civil servants, especially training to improve the qualifications of civil servants in the province, ensuring the requirements of professional qualifications as well as political opinion to Department for the province's development in terms of integration and development has achieved some results as follows:

Table 1: Results of training and fostering civil servants in Hoa Binh province over the years

Content	2016	2017	2018	2019
Training times	19,244	20,073	21,843	26,515
Funding (billion dong)	16.63	21.2315	15.71	17.9

Source: [6], [7], [8], [9]

In 2016, Hoa Binh province organized training and fostering for 19,244 turns of provincial civil servants , civil servants and public employees, with specific results as follows: 135 classes have been opened, with 11,027 turns of people from the provincial budget. ; opened 15 classes, with 765 people from the central budget; Training and fostering from the funding of agencies, units and civil servants , civil servants and public employees: 57 classes, with 7,452 turns of people, namely: Domestic training and fostering: 19,205 turns of people. Training 12 classes with 879 people; Fostering 195 classes, with 18,121 turns of people; Send 205 people to training in the country; Sent abroad for training and fostering: 39 turns of people. Total expenditure for training and fostering civil servants , civil servants in 2016 is 16.630.000.000 VND, of which: Central budget is 600,000,000 VND, provincial budget is 12,330,000,000 VND, other sources 3,700.000.000 VND [6].

In 2017, Hoa Binh province organized training and fostering for 20,073 turns of provincial civil servants , civil servants and public employees, with specific results as follows: 172 classes have been opened, with 12,552 turns of people from the provincial budget. ; opened 32 classes, with 1,804 people from the central budget; Training and fostering from the funding of agencies, units and civil servants , civil servants and public employees: 39 classes, with 5,717 turns of people. The total cost of training and fostering for civil servants , civil servants and public employees in 2017 is 21,231,952,000 VND, of which: Central budget is 1,875,000,000 VND, provincial budget is 16,556,952,000 VND, other sources 2,800.000.000 VND [7].

In 2018, Hoa Binh province organized training and fostering for 21,843 turns of provincial officials, civil servants and employees, including: Opening 103 classes, with 8,735 turns of people from the provincial budget; opened 23 classes, with 1,212 turns of people from funding sources to implement the national target program on building a new countryside; training and fostering by job positions, specialized knowledge and skills for civil servants , civil servants and public employees: 11,896 turns of people. The total cost of training and fostering for civil servants , civil servants and public employees in 2018 is 15,710,000,000 VND, of which: The central budget is 1,000,000,000 VND, the provincial budget is 11,710,000,000 VND, and other sources 3,000.000.000.000 VND [8]. In March 2018, the Member of the Provincial Party Committee coordinated with Ho Chi Minh National Politics Academy to organize a refresher course for leaders and managers of Hoa Binh province for the period 2015-2020 and 2020-2025 for 88 students come from departments, branches, unions, districts and cities in the province. At the end of the course, Mr. Hoang Minh Tuan, Head of the Provincial Party Committee's Organizing Committee, Deputy Head of the Class Steering Committee commented: "This is really a good start in the roadmap of professionalizing the province's civil servants" .

In 2019, Hoa Binh province opened 223 training and fostering classes for 26,515 turns of provincial officials, civil servants and public employees, including: Opening 125 classes, with 9,309 people from the provincial budget; opened 18 classes, with 1,087 turns of people from funding sources to implement the national target program on building a new countryside; opened 80 refresher courses based on job positions, specialized knowledge and skills for civil servants , civil servants and public employees: 16,119 turns of people. The total cost of training and fostering for civil servants , civil servants and public employees in 2019 is 17,900,000,000 VND, of which: Central budget 900,000,000 VND, provincial budget 12,000,000,000 VND, other sources 3,000,000,000 VND, funds contributed by organizations and individuals: 2,000,000,000 [9].

However, the proportion of grassroots civil servants who have not been trained or trained in the right profession or professional skills still accounts for a high percentage (expertise: 32.1%; political theory: 29.8%). The ability of cognizing, applying, concretizing and organizing the implementation of the Party's line, the State's policies and laws, directives and resolutions of superior committees is still weak. Capturing public opinion, discovering and solving complex problems occurring at the grassroots level, especially "hot" spots about rural security, social order, land disputes, property ... still embarrassed and passive. The inspection and supervision are not regular. The assessment, planning, training and fostering civil servants at a number of party committees and grassroots authorities have not been given adequate attention. Policies and regimes for civil servants have not created the motivation to attract qualified staff to the facilities in order to work.

2.2. General assessment

The results achieved above shows the advantages in the cadre training of Hoa Binh province as follows :

Training and fostering civil servants and public employees often receive attention, only leaders of the Provincial Party Committee, Provincial People's Committee and Ministry of Home Affairs. The contents of training and fostering have been reformed, mainly focusing on political theory; public servant category standards, professional titles for public employees; fostering job-solving skills according to job positions; especially focusing on fostering according to the standards of managerial positions . The agencies and units assigned the task of fostering have selected reputable training and fostering institutions; a team of highly qualified teachers with lots of practical experience to teach topics. Therefore, the quality of training and fostering has been improved step by step. Civil servants after participating in training and fostering, have applied knowledge they have applied effectively into practice, giving advice and performing assigned functions and tasks; the capacity and professional skills of civil servants , civil servants and public employees after training and fostering have been significantly raised.

Agencies, units and localities have paid attention to and created favorable conditions for civil servants to improve their professional qualifications, be fostered for completion according to the standards of civil servants and titles. Career officers and current employment positions assumed.

In addition to the achieved results, the training of civil servants in Hoa Binh province still has shortcomings :

The formulation of training plans, cost estimates for training and foresting, implementation of plans and statistical reports on training and foresting of a number of departments, branches and localities are still formality, slow progress and low quality. The survey and determination of training and fostering needs of some agencies and units have not yet surveyed reality.

The cost for training and fostering is still low, has not met the requirements, especially the funding for training according to the compulsory job position is at least 1 person/week/year for officials and public servants. The level of spending for fostering work is still low compared to the market reality, so it is difficult to organize the training and has not encouraged civil servants and public employees to actively participate in training.

A number of agencies, units and localities have not been close in organizing the implementation of plans for training, fostering to complete the professional title standards of public employees according to regulations.

The number of civil servants and public employees sent for training and fostering abroad is small; The number of civil servants who do not hold leadership positions or managers who are sent for training and fostering abroad accounts for a low rate; there is no provincial budget for the training of leading, civil servants and public employees working abroad.

The contingent of lecturers and reporters of the province are not of high quality, lack of people with high qualifications such as professors, associate professors, doctors, leading experts.

The cause of the limitations: The main reason is that the heads of some agencies, units and localities are not fully aware of the importance of training and fostering; The contingent of civil servants who advise on the training and fostering work is lacking knowledge and experience. Civil servants and public employees participating in training and fostering courses have not really stemmed from the needs of the job positions, the main motivation to study is to perfect

diplomas and certificates according to regulations. The assessment of training and fostering results has not been linked to the assessment of the level of fulfillment of the tasks of each civil servant or public employee.

2.3. Some solutions and recommendations

In order to better perform the training and foresting civil servants in Hoa Binh province, in the coming time, the province should apply the following solutions:

Heads of agencies, units and localities need to raise awareness about the role of training and fostering civil servants and public employees; Propagating and disseminating training and fostering work so that each officer, public servant and public employee is aware of the role of training and fostering, thereby determining rights, obligations and responsibilities in learning and self-study. It is clear that the characteristics of this contingent are close to the people, formed from many different sources, unequal in qualifications when recruiting such as district and provincial civil servants, some civil servants by the people elected. Many staff members working by experience are the main ones, operating in heterogeneous areas with low and uneven educational levels (especially in remote areas and highland areas), easily provoked, drag.

Strengthen the leadership and direction of districts and city commissars; the guiding and inspecting role of the advisory and assisting agencies of the committees and the specialized agencies. Understand the current state of the contingent of grassroots civil servants to have plans, measures to direct and guide to remove difficulties, problems and shortcomings. Reward individuals and units with outstanding achievements; summarize practice, replicate advanced practices, at the same time strictly and promptly handle violating officials. For weak establishments, identify the correct causes and take appropriate corrective action; resolutely resolve internal places where internal solidarity and weakness persist. On-site civil servants who fail to fulfill their duties and meet the requirements need to resolutely replace them with qualified, capable and experienced staff.

Strengthen state management; assign, decentralize and guide the procedures in training and fostering at the same time to encourage civil servants to study, concretize the rights and responsibilities of civil servants in choosing programs, the location and time for participating in training and fostering courses are suitable to the specific work, job position, and position held. Building title standards for the contingent of grassroots cadres and civil servants in line with socio-economic development orientation, characteristics of a mountainous province with diverse population composition and many ethnic minorities numbers live together. Standardize titles. Reviewing the number of grassroots cadres and civil servants who have not met the prescribed standards, then classify, arrange, and have plans to build, train and foster according to the specific roadmap. The standardization of grassroots civil servants in the direction: in communes, wards and townships that do well in planning work, and have a better source of replacement civil servants, arrange them for older and competent civil servants, limited capacity, not qualified to leave before age. For civil servants who are still old enough for re-election for the next term and still have credit but have not met the standards, must have the training and fostering plans are suitable.

Determine the appropriate ratio of ethnic minority civil servants and female civil servants to each locality and unit upon enrollment and recruitment. The training must diversify modes and types, suitable to the qualifications and ability to absorb knowledge and skills of grassroots civil servants. The training and fostering of grassroots civil servants is focused on: right subjects, with address. Attaching importance to training and fostering resource officers. Focusing on intensive fostering and training of working methods, skills in handling situations for leaders and managers; professional skills for professional staff; propaganda and advocacy skills for front staff, unions and part-time cadres in order to build a contingent of qualified civil servants. Renewing training forms, changing from long-term to short-term training and fostering in the form of training, seminars, on-the-job training, short-term training to overcome the psychology of studying away from home or difficult economic events. Rotating superior cadres to hold key positions at the grassroots level, considering this as a form of training so that staff can access, practice, grasp the practice, and help the establishment to build. construction, creating staff resources.

Attaching importance to resource officers who are students of boarding schools. At the same time, promote a contingent of prestigious, capable and responsible village elders and village chiefs. Amending and supplementing preferential policies to attract quality cadres; focus on students who are graduating with good quality, good at universities and graduate students working in the locality. See these as additional reserve civil servants for all levels in the province. Improve the quality of lecturers at the Provincial Political School, political fostering centers in districts and cities, and part-time lecturers. Combine theoretical training with practice, practice in depth, help improve practical capacity, have methods and skills to handle situations.

Thirdly, supplement the state budget for training and fostering; mobilize additional funding sources from collectives, individuals and society. Invest in building material foundations, ensure operating funding for socio-political organizations at the grassroots level, the provincial Political School and district political education centers. There are

policies to support grassroots civil servants to stabilize their income, support public service houses and some other regimes for cadres who move to grassroots to help them feel secure in their work.

III. CONCLUSION

Faced with the requirements of administrative reform, civil service reform, civil servant and international integration, besides the implementation of other contents of civil servants work, the MURA activities are increasingly playing an important role. . Therefore, improving the quality of training equipment, building a contingent of qualified, capable and reputable civil servants on a mission level must be performed regularly and continuously, is one of the important tasks in the work. civil servants of our Party and State in the coming time.

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